

Species	Osteoglycin 1 (OGN1)	Osteoglycin 2 (OGN2)
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	KJ891722	-
<i>Gorilla gorilla gorilla</i>	XM_004048267	-
<i>Pongo abelii</i>	NM_001132012	-
<i>Bos taurus</i>	BC102526	-
<i>Equus caballus</i>	XM_001917975	-
<i>Ovis aries</i>	XM_004004076	-
<i>Ceratotherium simum simum</i>	XM_004442726	-
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	XM_004313593	-
<i>Orcinus orca</i>	XM_004284119	-
<i>Mus musculus</i>	NM_008760	-
<i>Cricetulus griseus</i>	XM_003505338	-
<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	XM_006253696	-
<i>Gallus gallus</i>	NM_204209	-
<i>Taeniopygia guttata</i>	XM_002193078	-
<i>Ficedula albicollis</i>	XM_005052906	-
<i>Xenopus (Silurana) tropicalis</i>	ENSXETT00000045198	-
<i>Pelodiscus sinensis</i>	XM_006127563	-
<i>Chrysemys picta bellii</i>	XM_008165394	-
<i>Latimeria Chalumnae</i>	XM_005987054	-
<i>Lepisosteus oculatus</i>	XM_006631102	-
<i>Gadus morhua</i>	ENSGMOT00000003141	ENSGMOT00000004743
<i>Astyanax mexicanus</i>	ENSAMXT00000005237	ENSAMXT00000013872
<i>Danio rerio</i>	NM_001013570	ENSDARG00000031489
<i>Salmo salar</i>	BT056541	BT048437
<i>Oryzias latipes</i>	XM_004086123	-
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	DLAgn_00097140	DLAgn_00129310
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	ENSONIT00000000620	XM_003438862
<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>	XM_003973017	XM_003963383